

1 Transcriptomics of cancer resulting from HPV33 infection.

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7 We measured and compared total transcription in primary tumors from cervical cancers in humans
8 resulting from infection with known high-risk types HPV16 and HPV18 versus that of a third high-risk type,
9 HPV33. We report specific induction of *Krt10* in cervical cancers. HPV33-induced cervical cancers
10 displayed specific expression of Mme. In contrast, both HPV33+ cancers, HPV16+ cancers and HPV18+
11 cancers expressed *Rnf212*.

12 Citations

13 1. Ferguson, M., Wilkinson, D.E., Heath, A. and Matejtschuk, P., 2011. The first international
14 standard for antibodies to HPV 16. *Vaccine*, 29(38), pp.6520-6526.

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